

Article

The Role of Digital Libraries in Women Empowerment

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Abstract

Gender is an important dimension of social science research interrogates the social inequalities between men and women. It is evident that women are preoccupied with thousands of social boundaries prohibits in accessing social institutions. Consequently women are also accustomed to such restriction in the current era which is also made by the information society along with other important terms like democracy, equality and so forth. The following article is based upon the literature review which explains the relationships between gender and technology; the article may also justify the prospects of carrying out research in lines of gender and technology.

Key Words: Digital citizen, Digital divide, Digital Literacy, Gender

Web 2.0 is a new interactive platform of networking, that has radically changes the world surrounds us, it's not only changes the web interface, but at the same time incorporated huge masses in the world of active participation in networks. Evolution of Web2.0 is made Web3.0, which namely introduced intelligent web. Future development of

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Web2.0, hypothetically about a future wave of internet innovation is called Web3.0. It's have some good quality feature like semantic web system, data mining, machine learning, natural language search, recommendation agents and artificial intelligence of understanding semantics of information. Web 2.0 plays an important role by knowledge dissemination in our society. Web 2.0 is transformation relationship between users and information. Naturally, we must said that in present day Web3.0 took new several of research which technology trends in levels of maturity simultaneously including here. Web 2.0 has radically changes the interactive space of human interaction with each other, human and technology; where traditional social hierarchies and relationships are getting new shapes. The changes should come under close observations and new forms of social relationships between technologically created social spaces and traditionally shaped social relationships should be studied.

In today's networked society huge number of terminals has opened those were non-existence until recent past. Once an individual is connected, Internet connectivity and ICTs can enhance their future social and cultural capital. Social capital is acquired through repeated interactions with other individuals or groups of individuals. Connecting to the Internet creates another set of means by which to achieve repeated interactions. ICTs and Internet connectivity enable repeated interactions through access to social networks, chat rooms, and gaming sites. Once an individual has access to connectivity, obtains infrastructure by which to connect, and can understand and use the information that ICTs

and connectivity provide, that individual is capable of becoming a "digital citizen".[8] The rise of network society unleashed the immanent possibilities social networks from local to global. In networked societies boundaries are permeable, interactions are with diverse others, connections switch between multiple networks, and hierarchies can be flatter and recursive. The change from groups to networks can be seen at many levels. Trading and political blocs have lost their monolithic character in the world system. Organizations form complex networks of alliance and exchange rather than cartels, and workers report to multiple peers and superiors. Management by multiply-connected network is replacing management by hierarchal tree and management by two-dimensional matrix (Berkowitz 1982; Wellman 1988, Castells 1996).

In today's world digital libraries are important medium of advancing ones knowledge. In the context where societies are relying upon knowledge in terms of economic activities, libraries can play a significant role in the economic empowerment. The importance of libraries has been globally acknowledged over the period of time. Since time immemorial the presence of libraries can be trace in most advance civilizations of the world. Libraries are not only a source of archive of books rather a complete social environment where kinds of social relationships develop between people and the environment. In the context of modern education system the role of libraries are increasing, but the desired use of libraries is not yet optimized.

The concept of digital divide is relatively a new term to represent the inequality of cyber access by the people across the globe. The

concept first came into being during 1990's, which states the inequalities between societies in terms of accessing information recourses due to socio-economic disparities. The concept is should not be ideate as a holistic way, the term society is very broader where there are many social hierarchies which prohibits and inhibits social accessibilities across varied social hierarchies. Thus class, gender, caste, creed all are important dimensions should come under close scrutiny.

Gender is an important dimension of social science research; it is also philosophical stance which states the difference levels of social treatment to both sexes on the basic of culturally preoccupied notions. In social science there are number of specialized disciplines like sociology, women's studies, economics and others are actively engaged in doing research in exploring the visible and hidden aspects of gender inequalities. The nature and role of women in the society is presented by great heterogeneity, divergence and multiple paradoxical appearing phenomena as India itself. The nature and role of women in the society is presented by great heterogeneity, divergence and multiple paradoxical appearing phenomena as India itself. In order to remedy those conflicts, women are also requested to participate (NAAC, Jan,2015). Many women shared the common stereotypes and felt that men were needed at the top for the good of the profession. Some may have believed, mistakenly, that the large-scale entry of men into the profession would raise the salaries of all. Library education and librarianship seem to be good places to test the jobs available, gender available theory of gender stratification or segregation.

Therefore it is wise to choose feminism as an epistemological perspective of studying the library environment; it could explore the existing relationships between women and library. Methodologically speaking qualitative interviews in lines of social science research methods like ethnomethodological approaches may be helpful to the examination of men and women's place in the era of digitalization of libraries. There are limited number of social science research has been carried out towards understanding the relationships between libraries and society and more particularly the in lines of gender.

A society which is often characterized as a patriarchal society, where the some behaviors are considered as feminine and often downgraded. Social attitudes are largely a reflection of the social structure that is made by the masculine gender of the population. There is a need for a study of the social attitude on the use mobile phone by the female, most particularly in a heterogeneous culture like India, where mobile phone has just arrived and women's are also widely adopting it. It is evident that the early adoption of the telephone by the women and attitudinal differences by the society. In "Gender and the Residential Telephone, 1890-1940: Technologies of Sociability" Claude S. Fischer shown some example on the social attitude towards of telephony by the females in America, 'as it did for leaders of the early telephone industry, an implied derogation of women: that chatting on the telephone is "one more female foolishness." Social scientists know better.' The argument, in brief, is that women "appropriated" a practical, supposedly masculine technology for distinctively feminine

ends. This "gendering" of the telephone may have simultaneously reinforced gender differences and also amplified women's abilities to attain both their normatively prescribed and personally preferred ends. Women's telephony has been largely considered as a foolish act, without any practical end (Fischer, *Gender and the Residential Telephone 1890-1940: Technologies of Sociability*, 1988). In the gender stereotypes about women's telephone conversations, women are associated with "endless" chatting. These stereotypes are widespread and similar in various countries.

Technology, Women and Empowerment: Some example studies

In order to understand the relationship between technology and women, we need to take look of the woman's experience with technology so far in history. Here I like to cite some examples of the works of the social historians. The examples can give some idea on the way female adopted the new technology, social attitudes, social reforms and the way females use of the technology over the period of time.

Let's consider our first example of the bicycle as Smith shown "The few social historians of the bicycle seem to agree that many young women used it to shuck Victorian constraints. When mechanics developed a practical "safety bicycle" in the 1890s, middle-class Americans went on a virtual cycling craze. Since riding the contraption in contemporary ladies wear, bustles and all, was difficult, many women adopted risqué bloomer outfits and other shape-revealing clothes. This practice joined with a feminist movement against corsets and for freer garments, as well as an increasing

abandonment of Victorian inhibitions elsewhere.”[4]Here women have successfully challenged the imposed restriction on them in the form of traditional wear.“Bicycle outings also allowed young women to lose their chaperons and be alone with their beaux.”More and more women came to regard the bicycle as a freedom machine”.[4]Women begin to enjoy greater freedom and exceeding their socially imposed roles as ‘chaperons’ to ‘beaus’ at the advent of bicycle technology.

Another example can be drawn as the use of automobile. The automobile revolution has established the link which bonds the metropolis the pastoral life of America in the early part of 20th century. The women specially begin to come under ‘frequent touch with the entertainment and life of my neighboring small towns-with the joys of bargains, library, and soda-water’. [5]

Many women reportedly viewed the automobile as a device of personal liberation, especially for rural women. Perhaps this romance with the automobile turned into a snare. As the automobile became available to women, it also become necessary to them (for reasons mentioned above); trips were less often pleasant indulgences and more often unavoidable burdens. Still, in many ways and for many years, the automobile, too, seemed to amplify the ability of women to satisfy their own desires. [5]

Before we conclude we need to review the research findings on telephone and women. Researches, largely done by American Telephone and Telegraph (AT&T), indicates that today women are more likely to have telephones at home than are men; [6] that the

number of women or teenage girls in a household especially predict its frequency of calling; and that women initiate most of households' long distance calls [7]. An Ontario survey of people forty and older showed that women were two to three times more likely to telephone their friends than were men, although less than one-and-a-half times more likely than men to see their friends face-to-face found that in rural Wisconsin, "both women and men generally perceive the telephone to be part of women's domain." [8]

In Indian society on the formal restriction of the use of mobile phone by women. A village panchayat in Baghpat district of Uttar Pradesh, India - around 40 km from the nation's Capital - banned girls from using mobile phones when out on roads and women less than 40 years old from going out shopping. The decisions were taken by the panchayat in February 2012;[2]another instance where a village council in the eastern Indian state of Bihar has banned the use of mobile phones by women, saying the phones were "debasement the social atmosphere" by leading to elopements - a move that set off outraged protests from activists. In addition to the ban, the Sunderbari village council in a Muslim-dominated area some 385 kilometers (239 miles) east of Patna, the capital of Bihar, has also imposed a fine of 10,000 rupees if a girl is caught using a mobile phone on the streets. A married woman would have to pay 2,000 rupees."It always gives us a lot of embarrassment when someone asks who has eloped this time," said Manuwar Alam, who heads a newly-formed committee tasked with enforcing the ban, referring to queries from neighboring villages. He said the number of elopements and extramarital love affairs had

risen in the past few months, with at least six girls and women fleeing their homes."Even married women were deserting their husbands to elope with lovers. That was shameful for us," Alam said. "So, we decided to tackle it firmly. Mobile phones are debasing the social atmosphere".[3]

What appears from the news is that, there are definite perceptions on the use of mobile phone by the women in society in the form of formal, physical and symbolic. Thought the above instances cannot depict a general picture of Indian society at large. There is a need to sociological studies on the stereotypical notions on the mobile telephony by the female and changing attitude. Social history of other technology and women can explain the fact to an extent. For example, the social attitude on the bicycle use of the female.

Studies have confirmed that the phone is much needed device for women than men. "Census manuscripts to randomly sample a few hundred households in three northern California towns: Antioch, Palo Alto, and San Rafael. We then identified those that had residential telephones. In 1900, only 12 of 351 households had phones. None of the 39 households with unmarried male heads had residential telephones; 3 percent of the 203 households with male heads with wives but no daughters eighteen or older at home did; but 9 percent of the 35 households with husbands, wives, and at least one adult daughter had telephones. In 1910, the estimates were 12 percent of the 33 households headed by single males, 28 percent of the 229 with husband and wife but no adult daughters, and 44 percent of the 27 households with husband, wife, and daughter had telephones. (Households headed by females

were few and unusual." The study confirmed the positive correlation between the women and the household telephone.

In an another study on official investigations of rural life, especially of farm women, emphasized its isolation and boredom, and as in the 1909 Country Life Commission recommended or applauded improved communications, including the telephone. [9]A 1915 inquiry, "Social and Labor Needs of Farm Women" (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 1915), highlighted the "loneliness, isolation, and lack of social and educational opportunity" described by its respondents [10] and relayed requests by farm women for improved communications. Most asked for better roads, but some women also mentioned telephones, such as this one from Arkansas: "The worst trouble we have is isolation, absence of social life. The study concluded that women felt the need of a phone since its inception.[11]

A news report suggests that, Afghanistan has launched a new literacy programme that enables Afghan women deprived of a basic education during decades of war to learn to read and write using a mobile phone. The phone is called Ustad Mobile (Mobile Teacher) and provides national curriculum courses in national languages, Dari and Pashto, as well as mathematics. According to the program director, Allah Baz Jam, "Our focus and target is mostly on uneducated women". The goal is that this program will help women who were unable to attend school because of the Taliban rules that barred their access to an education.[12]

The above suggests that bicycle, automobile and telephone are in common in terms of the technologies of sociability; they facilitate

personal interaction and empowering women. The argument, in brief, is that women "appropriated" a practical, supposedly masculine technology for distinctively feminine ends. This "gendering" of the telephone may have simultaneously reinforced gender differences and also amplified women's abilities to attain both their normatively prescribed and personally preferred ends. An instrument created by masculine society to solve some instrumental function, whereas women brought the whole society in it.

Some Critical Insights

Most of this scholarship has contested the notion that mechanization of housework "liberated" women- notions promulgated by advertisers, Progressive era commentators, home economists, and many women themselves. "Verily," wrote a Women's Club leader in 1905, "the march of mechanical invention has been the emancipation of women. The freeing of their hands has led to the freeing of their mind (Wilson, 1979).

Now the question is whether patriarchal social structure have not imposed any restriction or recommendation on the use of technology by women. The answer is no, in a 1904 advertisement by the Delaware and Atlantic Company depicts a homemaker in an elegant Victorian dress speaking into a wall- mounted telephone. The text reads:" The modern way is to save one's time and temper by telephoning. The telephone makes housekeeping simple and emergencies no longer terrifying (Fischer & Carroll, The diffusion of the telephone and the automobile in the United States, 1902 to 1937., 1988).¹⁴Bell companies recommended that a man order an extension telephone for his wife's

bedside should she hear a prowler while he was away on business. But the dominant theme in marketing the telephone to women into the 1920s (Fischer & Carroll, The diffusion of the telephone and the automobile in the United States, 1902 to 1937., 1988)was the suggestion that women, in their roles as "chief executive officers" of the household, use the instrument to order goods and services. This was consistent with the emerging image of the housewife-administrator in both advertising and home economics (Marchand, 1985)

From that position we might seek to answer some questions like; has capitalist technology liberated women ever than before, or in structural term, has women constitutes a different social structure parallels with masculine society. If yes, then let's examine the criticisms on differential use of technology by the scholars over time. Telephone advertisements counseled women to use the instrument at home to manage the household, in particular to order supplies, call service people, and issue and respond to invitations (Steele, 1905)

Social historians like Cowan (1983) and others have argued that "common use of the automobile increased housework burdens on women by stimulating new shopping and chauffeuring trips, by undercutting delivery services, neighborhood stores, and other conveniences that had existed for the housebound housewife, and indirectly by expediting suburbanization and its consequent requirement for numerous and long trips.[17]Granting this point (for the moment- we have little solid evidence), there was also another side to the automobile In the current instance, given the extant gender division of

labor, it would seem that the telephone made women's work easier. There is little evidence to claim that women performed more (or fewer, for that matter) material tasks in the home because of the telephone. [18] While on the other hand, it is argue recent scholars, "industrialization of the home," although easing the arduousness of housework nevertheless continued and even solidified women's disproportionate responsibility for domestic labor. For example, advances in cleaning technology raised the standards for cleanliness that housewives must attain. [19] A Marxist feminist like Lana Rakow might argue that, "It is reasonable to claim, that the telephone made women more vulnerable to requests for their socio-emotional labor-to advice, comfort, organize, and so on. Women's tasks in this realm may have grown. But calls go both ways and it is likely that each burdensome call a woman received was matched by at least one help-seeking call a woman made."

The above reflect the realities of the American society of the early 20th century, where feminist movements has been allowed by the contemporary American society, which can be marked as a distinguish socio cultural environment, having a long history of equalitarian rights movements. There is a need for a study on the women's accessibility on the use of technology.

Conclusions

Every research works are pre occupied with certain philosophical stance, which guides the subsequent stages of the research. The central arguments of feminism may help to carry out a

research by considering gender as an important dimension of masculine and feminine perception of library as an important source of advancement. There is a need of intensive studies in lines of gender on the use of digital libraries, the levels of digital literacy, the levels of technological availability, internet access in the current society.

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